

LECTURE AS THE LEADING METHOD OF TRAINING IN THE PROFESSIONAL ACTIVE OF A MODRN PHYSICIAN

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Annotation: The article presents the features of lecturing at the Samarkand State Medical University of the Republic of Uzbekistan, shows the role and place in the organization of the educational process in modern medical education, shows methods for improving the quality of education, the prospects for it's development, the advantage of visual teaching aids.

Key words: lecture, educational process, medical education, new technologies

Аннотация: В статье представлены особенности чтения лекций в Самаркандском государственном медицинском университете Республики Узбекистан, показаны роль и место в организации учебного процесса в современном медицинском образовании, показаны методы повышения качества образования, перспективы его развития, преимущество наглядных средств обучения.

Ключевые слова: лекция, учебный процесс, медицинское образование, новые технологии.

Medical education is one of the most promising and sought-after areas of higher education, characterized by the duration of training, complexity, variety of curricula and the peculiarity of educational tasks. However, today it is available to everyone, including foreign students. Obtaining a high-quality medical education is important for the production of highly qualified specialists [1,2].

Currently, lectures are an organic part of the medical education system of institutes, they require improvement based on scientific research, sound approaches to the construction of modern lectures, and evaluation of their effectiveness.

In this regard, the solution to the problem of improving the effectiveness of lectures in medical schools is relevant in scientific, theoretical and practical terms.

It is known that a doctor must learn all his life. A Chinese proverb says: "Learning is like rowing against the current: as soon as you stop, you are driven back."

In the age of information technology, knowledge becomes obsolete quickly, so it is very important to constantly update and improve its level.

At present, there have been significant qualitative changes in the field of higher education of medical universities, a three-stage model of personnel training generally accepted in world practice has been introduced: bachelor's degree, master's degree, doctorate. Today, along with the preservation of the best achievements, important changes are needed, such as stimulating the scientific and clinical thinking of students, providing them with knowledge, skills and abilities.

Along with practical exercises, the lecture is traditionally the leading form of education at the university. A special place is occupied by clinical lectures, which have long been used by clinicians as a special form of development of clinical thinking, complicity, establishing an atmosphere of trust, partnerships, adherence to the principles of deontology [3,7,8]. even the Internet succeeds. The expression of the ancients "viva vox docet" ("living voice teaches") remains true, since the lecturer uses live sound. At present, the Internet is available for all students of the Samarkand State Medical Institute during classes and at home, the E-Learning System has been created and revised, i.e. a single educational portal of the institute was organized. In addition, along with traditional information resources, to ensure the process of distance learning, a large set of distance learning tools is used: specialized textbooks with multimedia accompaniments, electronic textbooks, manuals, computer laboratory workshops, tests, educational films, videos on practical exercises and practical skills, situational tasks in all disciplines and courses. Students prepare in advance for the lecture material, which is available on the website of the Institute in the E-Learning System, each student uses the materials of practical classes and lectures at any time convenient for him, which contributes to better assimilation of the material. Today, the experience of holding teleconferences, webinars, when leading teachers give lectures to students, has been mastered. [1,5]

In the educational process, the lecture form of education performs the following functions:

- informational - provides consistent information, performs the function of the main source of information, when new scientific data on a particular topic are not reflected in textbooks or manuals and the topics are very difficult for independent study and development;
- motivating - arouses interest in the topic;
- educating - disciplines students;
- developing - evaluates phenomena, concretizes and develops thinking, encourages the student to professionally think, reason, compare, analyze problems;
- orienting - in the tasks, problem, literature;
- explaining - aimed primarily at the formation of basic science;
- persuasive - with an emphasis on the system of evidence;
- scientific - gives new directions, modern achievements of science, the latest scientific problems.

The achieved result of the lecture is directly dependent on the method of its presentation and information technology support. It is known that the qualities of a clinical lecture include: content, methodology, student work management, teaching style, class effectiveness [2,6].

The lecturer must know the peculiarity of the classroom, time and other factors in preparing for a lecture, the quality of the lecture, which is expressed by the authority of the lecturer, the level of his knowledge, and his professional training, largely contributes to the assimilation of the material. A real scientist-teacher presents his subject with conviction, enthusiasm, which is an indispensable condition for arousing interest among students, there must be a contact between the teacher and students. Much depends on how the teacher presents himself, i.e. creates a positive image. The lecturer must have oratory, the voice, tempo, intonation, facial expressions and gestures of the lecturer are important, he must be able to subjugate the audience, create confidence in his knowledge, emotionally influence the student, observe the principles of ethics and deontology [1,3]. The lecture should be simple and clear ("The language of science is short"), the material should be varied, arouse the interest of the student. There is such a rule: "lectures must be read loudly enough to be heard, and at the same time,

quietly enough to be listened to." As Professor S.M. Korneev said, "in lectures, the freshness of the material should be felt, the breath of time should be felt".

Consequently, the quality of training of specialists depends on the pedagogical competence of a scientist, his professional and personal characteristics [1,4].

A "good" lecture is:

- the presence in the content of humanitarian goals and values, moral potential;
- scientific, informative, conclusive, argumentative content, the presence of vivid convincing examples, facts;
- a clear structure and logic of material disclosure; - methodological literacy of setting goals and objectives, identifying the main and secondary, drawing conclusions, using feedback;
- emotionality of the form of lecturing, the use of novelty, asking questions and involving students in clinical thinking;
- use of visual aids
- increases the interest of students in the lecture.

Such animated presentations are used, which include information on the topic of the lecture, illustrations (drawings, photographs, pictures, etc.). In addition, at present, the use of video materials is considered a promising direction; videos, films, animated materials are included in the lecture, which increases student interest, memorability, attention intensity, and increases cognitive activity. Lectures are usually delivered using multimedia.

At the same time, new innovative forms of lecture teaching are recommended:

1. Problematic lectures presented by two lecturers. These lectures are built in a problematic context, provide students with a creative assimilation of the principles and patterns of the course of the pathological process, assimilation of knowledge and their application in practice. So, in the formation of a scientific worldview among doctors, the ability to critically comprehend the flow of new information, a fundamental role is played by such disciplines as physics, chemistry, biology, therapy, surgery, anesthesiology-resuscitation, endocrinology, etc. When reading problematic lectures in clinical disciplines, it is advisable to expand inter-departmental cooperation and attract lecturers in other specialties for in-depth study of any problem. The relevance of such cooperation is increasing today at the Samarkand State Medical Institute in connection with the use of modular study of educational material by topic or section. Therefore, it is advisable to strengthen scientific and practical integration and interdepartmental cooperation between departments, especially in senior courses.
2. Lectures with visualization - visualization of lecture material is one of the types of technological support for training. The use of information innovations, the use of multimedia technology can improve the effectiveness of training.
3. Lecture with pre-planned errors - the lecturer controls the opinion of students, reveals erroneous opinions, and thereby contributes to the development of thinking, while students' attention to the lecture material increases and they remember better.
4. Lecture - conference or council. When presenting a lecture, the lecturer, asking questions to the student, organizes a free exchange of opinions during the transition of various subsections, which enlivens the lecture. The discussion of the lecturer's communication with the students allows not only to interest the student, but also to increase the perception of the lecture material.

Therefore, special preparation for the lecture is necessary, a revision of the methods of presenting the lecture, i.e. refocusing on visual aids.

At the end of each lecture, a list of literature and sites is given, according to which the student studies further at home.

Thus, the use of new technologies, a competent approach in medical education, the transition mainly to visual aids developed at the departments are promising for improving the quality of lecture support and the study of medical discipline, contribute to lectures becoming in demand in the practice of higher education, as well as to train doctors, meeting high requirements and modern world standards. The education system should become more diverse, increase the significance and quality of education at all levels.

Conclusions:

1. It is possible to improve the quality of lectures by using the material from the e-learning system developed by the staff of the departments.
2. The use of new technologies for presenting lecture material (mainly visual aids) helps to improve the quality of education.
3. It is necessary to strengthen scientific and practical integration and interdepartmental cooperation between theoretical and practical departments.

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